

Uranium (IV) Carboxylates - I

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A few uranium(IV) carboxylates with monochloro and trichloro acetic acid, glycine, malic, citric, adipic, *o*-toluic, anthranilic and salicylic acids have been prepared by photolytic methods. The i.r. spectra of these compounds are recorded and basing on the spectral data structure of the compounds have been suggested.

THE carboxylates of uranium(IV) are complex salts of high coordination number. A number of uranium(IV) carboxylates have been reported earlier by different methods¹⁻¹⁰ but very little study has been made on the structural aspect of the carboxylates. In the present study an attempt has been made to prepare a few more new carboxylates and their structures have been suggested.

Methods and Materials

The chemicals used were either of Analar B.D.H. or fluka qualities. The following methods are used to prepare the carboxylates.

(A) An aqueous solution of uranyl formate (about 2 g) were reduced to uranium(IV) state by exposing to sunlight in presence of a few ml. of formic acid and alcohol. The reduced solution was treated with an aqueous solution of the appropriate acids (monochloro acetic acid, trichloro acetic acid, glycine, malic acid and citric acid) so that the ratio of uranium(IV) to acid ion was 1 : 3, when a green precipitate was formed. The resulting solution along with the precipitate formed was further exposed to sunlight for 8-10 hr. The compound obtained was filtered, washed with water followed by ethanol, dried in vacuum and analysed.

(B) An aqueous solution of 2 g of uranyl formate was prepared in minimum quantity of water. The solution was exposed to sunlight with a few ml. of formic acid and alcohol. The uranium(IV) solution thus obtained was treated with a solution of the appropriate acids (adipic, *o*-toluic, anthranilic and salicylic acids) in ethanol, when a green precipitate was formed. The precipitate was filtered, washed with ethanol several times, dried in vacuum and analysed.

The uranium content of the compounds were estimated as U_3O_8 . The carboxylate content calculated from the percentage of carbon and hydrogen. In certain cases it has been estimated by acid alkali titration. The chloride and nitrogen were determined by standard methods. The formula computed

for the carboxylates and the analytical data are given in Table 1.

All the compounds are green in colour, insoluble in water (except glycinate) and organic solvents. They are soluble in dilute mineral acids forming green solution. Bases such as NaOH or ammonia precipitate hydrated uranium(IV) oxide. The compounds slowly undergo oxidation on long keeping in atmospheric air.

The i.r. spectra of the carboxylates have been studied with a view to get information on the most probable structure of the compounds. The spectral data are recorded in Table 2.

Discussion

The vibrational spectra of alkali carboxylates and complexes of carboxylic acid have been studied extensively¹¹. The antisymmetric (O-C-O) stretching vibration is most sensitive to change in the metal ion and the relationship between this frequency and the physical properties of the metal ion has been the subject matter of discussion by a number of workers. Theimer and Theimer¹² have suggested that the radius of the metal ion is the important factor in determining the position of the ν as (O-C-O) band. Kagarise¹³, on the other hand, claims that the electronegativity of metal ion to be more important. Ellis *et al.*¹⁴ have suggested that the (O-C-O) stretching vibration depends on several functions such as mass, radius and electronegativity of the metal ion.

The carboxylate ion may be bonded to metallic ion in four different ways (Figs. I-IV).

The i.r. data have been explained on the basis of structural data available from X-ray studies for various structures. In sodium formate the bond is ionic and both C-O bonds are of equal length (1.27 Å) as in Fig. I. On the otherhand, $Li(Ac) \cdot 2H_2O$

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TABLE I. ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE CARBOXYLATES OF URANIUM (IV)

Name of the compounds with formula	Uranium%		Carbon%		Hydrogen%		Nitrogen% or Halogen%		Carboxylate%	
	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1. Uranium(IV) dihydroxo- di(monochloro) acetate. [U(OH) ₂ (ClCH ₂ COO) ₂].H ₂ O	49.98	49.90	9.45	10.07	1.69	1.67	7.08	7.46	—	—
2. Uranium(IV) dihydroxo- di(trichloro)acetate. [U(OH) ₂ (Cl ₃ CCOO) ₂].3H ₂ O.	38.08	37.60	7.96	7.58	1.30	1.48	5.60	5.31	—	—
3. Uranium(IV)tetra-glycinate [U(NH ₂ CH ₂ COO) ₄].1.5H ₂ O.	42.71	42.42	16.61	17.11	3.51	3.38	—	—	—	—
4. Uranium(IV)dimalonate U(C ₆ H ₈ O ₄) ₂ .0.5H ₂ O	52.93	52.77	—	—	—	—	—	—	46.17	45.33
5. Uranium(IV)dia-pate U(C ₆ H ₈ O ₄) ₂ .0.5H ₂ O	44.89	44.58	—	—	—	—	—	—	54.75	53.94
6. Uranium(IV)oxo citrate UO(C ₆ H ₆ O ₇)	53.98	53.60	—	—	—	—	—	—	43.70	43.57
7. Uranium(IV) dihydroxo ditoluate U[(OH) ₂ (C ₈ H ₇ O ₂) ₂]	44.07	43.75	35.35	35.29	2.61	2.94	—	—	—	—
8. Uranium(IV)dihydroxo dianthramalate. U[(OH) ₂ (NH ₂ C ₆ H ₆ COO) ₂].2H ₂ O.	40.61	41.04	28.44	29.96	2.36	3.10	4.78	4.26	—	—
9. Uranium(IV)disalicylate U(C ₇ H ₄ O ₃) ₂ .2H ₂ O.	43.65	43.59	29.75	30.48	2.30	2.29	—	—	—	—

TABLE 2. PRINCIPAL i.r. BANDS OF URANIUM (IV) CARBOXYLATES

Compound	$\nu_{as}(\text{OCO})$	$\delta_{(\text{OH})}$	$\nu_s(\text{OCO})$	$\nu(\text{CH})\nu(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	Phenolate(C-O)
*NaOAc	1578 s	—	1480 s	—	—
*K ₂ Mal.nH ₂ O	1563 s	—	1405 s 1370	3460 s 3300 3200 2900	—
*Na ₂ Mal.H ₂ O	1600 s 1562 s	—	1390 1370	3420 3120 2970	—
*Na ₂ Cu(Mal) ₂ .H ₂ O	1610 s 1590 s	—	1410 m 1370 m	3300 3200 2900	—
*U(OH)(OAC) ₃	1545 s 1515 s	1290 m 1260 m	1410 s 1345 s	3500 s 3200 msh	—
U(OH) ₂ (ClCH ₂ COO) ₂ .H ₂ O	1600 s	1280 s	1475 s 1450 s 1425 s	3536 sb	—
U(OH) ₂ (CCl ₃ COO) ₂ .3H ₂ O	1600 s	1285	1400 s	3350 s	—
U(NH ₂ CH ₂ COO) ₄ .1.5H ₂ O	1625 s	—	1425 s	3400—3000 sb.	—
U(Mal) ₂ .H ₂ O	1550 s	—	1370 s	3390 s	—
U(adip) ₂ .0.5H ₂ O	1538 s	—	1380 s	3330 s 2915 m	—
UO(Cit)	1631—1520 sbd	—	1480—1379 sbd	3500—3000 sbd	1090 s
U(OH) ₂ (anthra) ₂ .2H ₂ O	1650—1520 mbd	1280	1370 m	3550—3000 sbd	1045 m
U(sali) ₂ .2H ₂ O	1675—1590 m	1245 s	1330 s	3200 s	1030 m
U(OH) ₂ (tolu) ₂	1610 s	1230 s	1405 s	3300 m	1105 m

OAC—acetate, Mal—Malonate, adip—adipitate, Cit—Citrate[(CH₂)₂C(OH)COOHCOO]²⁻, anthra—anthranalate, Sali—Salicylate, tolu—ortho toluate. * literature values.

adopts structure II, the two CO bond lengths being unequal (1.33 Å and 1.22 Å) and this structure occurs most frequently among the carboxylates of higher valent metal ions. The four membered ring structure where both the oxygen atoms of the carboxylate groups are bonded to the same metal ion is rather rare. Only a few carboxylates such as Na [UO₂(Ac)₃], Zn(Ac)₂ · 2H₂O, Cr(Ac)₃ and Mn(Ac)₃ adopt this structure. The bridged structure (Fig. IV) is found for Cr₂(Ac)₄ · 2H₂O, Cu₂(Ac)₄ · 2H₂O, Be₄O(Ac)₆ and Zn₃O(Ac)₆ compounds. Recently from X-ray studies the bridged structure has been suggested for uranium(IV) tetra acetate, U(CH₃COO)₄.

As can be seen from Table 2 the ν as (O-C-O) vibration in alkali carboxylates is located in the region 1563–1600 cm⁻¹ and in metal complexes, it shifts towards higher frequency region. In alkali salts there is greater electron delocalisation within (O-C-O) group making both C-O bonds equivalent, but in the metal chelates one C-O bond is lengthened due to bonding with metal ion and another (C-O) bond is shortened and hence the above changes in the spectra. Another significant fact is the splitting of the ν as (O-C-O) and ν s (O-C-O) bands, possibly due to inequivalence of both the CO groups within the same (O-C-O) group.

The positions of the ν as (O-C-O) band for the uranium(IV) acetates, dimalonate and diadipate are located at 1600–1625, 1550, and 1538 cm⁻¹ respectively. They are unsplit (narrow width) and suggest both CO groups within the same (OCO) group to be equivalent. From all available knowledge, the actinide elements in all their oxidation states may be regarded as Chatt-Ahrland A-type ions, form strong covalent bonds with less polarisable ions or groups such as F⁻ or oxygen containing ligands. Coordination number is usually high (6–10), eight being more predominant. For these reasons i.e., a considerable low value of ν as (OCO) band and Chatt-Ahrland A-type character, the bonding pattern in these carboxylates may be either of the type (Figure-III) or (Figure-IV). But it is not possible to distinguish between the two structures from the vibrational spectra. The structure of uranium(IV) tetraacetate has been determined from X-ray studies, where each acetate group act as a bridging ligand between a pair of uranium(IV) ions. The carboxylates under discussion have a light green fibrous look as U(Ac)₄. They are all insoluble (except the glycinate) in water and several organic solvents and may be regarded as polymers and therefore believed to possess similar structure as U(Ac)₄, uranium being eight coordinate.

In sharp contrast to the above carboxylates the ν as(OCO), and ν s(OCO) band in citrate of uranium(IV) are broad (Table 2). These bands certainly represent doublets of the split ν as(OCO) and ν s(OCO) band as bonded in a manner as shown in Fig. V.

The C-O stretching frequency of the secondary alcoholic group are reported to occur in the region

1060–1080 cm⁻¹. In uranium(IV) citrate it is located at 1090 cm⁻¹ and seem to be coordinated to U⁺⁴ in order to satisfy its coordination sphere.

Fig. 5.

The ν as(O-C-O) vibration of the three aromatic carboxylates of uranium(IV) are located in the region 1625–1675 cm⁻¹ and that of ν s(O-C-O) vibration are in the region 1330–1429 cm⁻¹ (Table 2). Besides, the phenolate group is located in the region 1030–1060 cm⁻¹. The stoichiometry and position of the ν as (O-C-O) band and phenolic (CO) band logically suggest the structure to be as shown in Fig. VI, the sphere of coordination being further filled by the water moleculust.

Fig. VI.

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References

1. B. SAHOO and D. PATNAIK, *Current Sci.* 1958, **27**, 243.
2. D. PATNAIK and B. SAHOO, *Current Sci.*, 1958, **27**, 292.
3. K. K. TRIPATHY, B. SAHOO and D. PATNAIK. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1959, **36**, 739.
4. B. SAHOO and D. PATNAIK. *Current Sci.*, 1960, **29**, 16.
5. U. K. DAS, S. K. PUJARI, B. SAHOO and D. PATNAIK, *Current Sci.*, 1961, **30**, 380.
6. B. SAHOO. *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, **2**, 75.
7. B. SAHOO and D. PATNAIK. *Nature*, 1960, **185**, 883.
8. R. C. PAUL, J. S. GHOTRA and M. S. BAINS. *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 265.
9. J. SELBIN, N. SCHOEBER and J. ORTHEGO. *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 1385.
10. K. C. SATPATHY and B. SAHOO. *Current Sci.*; 1967, **36**, 320.
11. M. J. SCHMELZ, Ichiro Nakagaiwa, Sonnichiro Mizushima and J. V. Duogliano. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*; 1959, **81**, 287.
12. R. THEIMER and O. THEIMER. *Montsh.* 1950, **81**, 313.
13. R. E. KAGERISE. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, **59**, 271.
14. B. ELLIS and H. PSYZORA, *Nature*, 1958, **181**, 181.